

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/275970919>

A CYCLIC MODEL OF GALAXY EVOLUTION WITH BARS (Published HJ 2014)

Research · May 2015

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.4540.5603

CITATIONS

0

READS

1,993

2 authors:

Peter Jackson

Royal Astronomical Society

22 PUBLICATIONS 21 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

John S Minkowski

Johns Hopkins Medicine

17 PUBLICATIONS 245 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

A CYCLIC MODEL OF GALAXY EVOLUTION WITH BARS

Peter A Jackson¹ and John S. Minkowski.² v4a. March 2014.

¹RAS, AAS, Orchard House Hillside Rd. Whitstable CT5 3EX, UK

²Baltimore, Maryland, USA, MD 21204. jminkow1@jhmi.edu

Abstract

We present a cyclic model of galaxy evolution deriving bars and peculiar structure. Conceptual 'toy' models are important tools supporting simulations. We correlate SDSS, kinetic and other survey findings, and present evidence of an iterative process powered by galactic nuclei (AGN) orbital angular momentum. Focused on the “quasar-era's” at $z \sim 6 \gg z \sim 1.7$ AGN's accrete, re-ionize and eject disc matter in collimated jets on the disc axis. Assumed feedback to discs is replaced by disc clearance and creation of a new open spiral on the new perpendicular axis of re-ionized jet matter. The bar half-length is the virial radius. Spiral arms formed from the jet matter tighten and blend into discs as commonly assumed. We find accretion forms lenticular bulges as outflows create the lobes. Rings may then result from accretion. A cycle of active quasar population was identified at ~ 10 Gyr by Martini-Weinberg (2001). [¹] Metallicity/star-forming evolution suggests similar 'multiple infall' events (Micali-Matteucci-Romano (2013). [²] We predict a tranche of anomalous observed phenomena including superluminal jets consistent with a Friedman universe, halo kinematic decoupling, anisotropic mass growth at $z \sim 6$ and $z \sim 2$, the accompanying re-ionization of H and He in turn, single age dwarf satellite galaxies and the Magellanic stream.

Keywords: galaxy dynamics; galaxy formation & evolution; galaxy structure and formation; nuclei: quasars: general; re-ionization; cyclic cosmology: non-linear dynamics.

1 Introduction

A key process in galaxy evolution is feedback, principally of matter from AGN outflows and jets of accreted disc material, back to discs via the halo. Accreted and ejected volumes are established as very significant, but observational evidence of feedback from jets remains elusive. NASA's HST *Cosmic Origins Spectrograph* (COS) should allow data from gas flows around 50 galaxies in the UV from a 2013 survey and dynamic simulations. Covering the little probed gap from 2 -10 billion years ago the project; "*A Breakaway from Incremental Science: Full Characterization of the Circumgalactic Medium and Testing Galaxy Evolution Theory.*" should find evidence of any feedback. We predict that the survey will find no significant feedback from the high powered jet element of outflows, which will leave a theoretical problem. The cyclic model we present is able to explain a no-feedback scenario and predicts a quite different dynamic pattern based on the quasar.

The precise role of AGN's and quasars in evolution has never been explained. In 1964 John Wheeler famously said in desperation when boarding a flight with four quasar physicists; "*If this plane were to crash, we could get a new start on this quasar problem.*" We now suggest a direction for such a new start, giving quasars and the AGN's that power them the leading roles. Quasar feedback dynamics are commonly assumed to contribute to the complex star formation patterns in a way not yet explained, and so drive secular galaxy evolution. The increase in mass and size of galaxies since the early universe has been attributed to mergers, also assumed to affect morphology in some way not understood. We do not review common evolutionary theories here but do recognise that feedback theory is also beset by unresolved problems. Dynamic modelling of feedback remains problematic, thereby limiting galaxy evolution simulation. Vogelsberger et al (2103) [3] found the need to invoke "*very strong forms of stellar and AGN feedback*" to suppress efficient cooling in haloes. Energetic quasar outflow rates are identified by Liu et al (2013) [4] as; "*bound to make a strong impact on the formation of massive galaxies*" Liu estimates outflow periods $\sim 1.8 \times 10^7$ yrs. We agree with the time scale but describe an apparently more consistent evolutionary model including full morphological

cycles with a unique new 'feedback' dynamic. We identify and describe how our cyclic model derives a wide range of peculiar galaxy characteristics. Particular variations to many popular current theories are identified.

1.1 Modelling and Sources

Conceptual 'toy' models have shown their value as important tools in laying sound foundations for computer simulations. The model we outline emerged from wide observational input and falsification of possible complex solutions by consistency of correlation. The COS survey project discussed above has a stated philosophy of finding strategic coherence and patterns from incremental findings. We use a consistent approach. Our iterative model emerged from the initial evaluation process, appearing to produce unique and falsifiable predictions widely consistent with observed patterns. This paper is the initial report describing the predictions and evidence which require wide investigation and testing including against the COS project data and dynamic simulations. Investigation work included examination of analysis of the SDSS based Galaxy Zoo-1 (GZ1) classifications of ~900,000 galaxies, (Lintott et al, 2010) [5] GZ2 of 304,122 galaxies (Willett 2013), [6]AGN's, bar analysis of 3,150 local disc galaxies (Hoyle 2011), [7] Fermi (Cabrera et al, 2013), [8] NASA Lambda CMB archive, *COMBI*, Hershel and *CANDELS* (near-IR UDS) findings (Barro et al, 2013). [9]We also reviewed kinetic analysis from the *Sauron* (Davis et al, 2001), [10] and *ATLAS^{3D}* surveys.

1.2 Outline and Sections

In the cyclic model which emerged, all disc matter is accreted, re-ionized and ejected, but does not then returned to the 'old' disc. When the fuel of old disc matter is depleted the re-ionized jet matter remains for a short period in a column resembling an 'edge on' disc, and the AGN activity dies. Intrinsic rotation at a virial radius commences on the perpendicular axis of the column, often before AGN expiry. The rotating centre of the column forms a new barred open spiral galaxy. A new nucleus forms with building angular momentum on the new axis, slowly building momentum by accretion. The cycle continues with the intuitive tightening of spiral arms, and slow blending into discs. Lenticular bulges grow from accretion and from axial lobe development driven

by the rebuilding AGN outflows. Evidence of the bar will normally remain but bar residue is eventually accreted into the bulge with the disc matter. Accretion to the core starts at the inner disc and works outwards. At low energies the accretion disc scale is found to be small and local to the core but we propose that ultimately and at peak energy almost all the old disc matter is accreted.

In section 2 we discuss overall trends and temporal morphological population distributions (TPD's). Section 3 briefly considers the effects of Intrinsic Rotation and Virial Radii invoked. The toy model is then described conceptually and graphically in section 4 including phenomenological construction and bar formation. The underlying mechanisms and components proposed are considered in part 5 and relativistic quasar jet superluminal motion is considered and derived in section 6. The inherent mechanisms producing Kinematic Halo Decoupling and Dwarf Satellite Galaxies are described in section 7 and a reference to implied fractal dynamics is made in section 8 before summarizing.

2 Trends and Morphological Distribution

An initial review of overall trends studied patterns which are often 'above the radar' of detailed and incremental surveys. We found anisotropic change to a number of fundamental galaxy characteristics which tend to be focussed at around $z \sim 2$. Based on significantly less data certain similarities exist with the area at $z > 6$. Both of these periods coincide with significant recognised peaks of quasar activity. Evidence exists that this correlation may not be coincidental, a view implied by (Barai et al 2004), [11]Nesvadba et al, 2010). [12] In morphological terms early universe galaxies closely replicated those of today. But this similarity presents two problems; a) The early universe versions evolved towards $z \sim 3$ to a greater predominance of redder disc galaxies. b) Mass and size of corresponding morphologies is greater in the local universe by factors of ~ 4 and 10 (Cimatti, Nipoti & Cassata, 2012). [13] The redder galaxy bias then seemed to give way to a predominance of bluer, ostensibly younger, spirals. Both the type and mass changes appear to be focused around the era's corresponding to the two peaks in quasar populations and activity.

Star formation rates and patterns are closely linked to morphology so also vary anisotropically with z factor. The high star formation rates at lobes is consistent when correlated with other galaxy characteristics but the population of active lobes may not be consistent throughout the life of the universe. The repeating patterns themselves may imply some sort of cyclic process. The underlying continued reduction of total star formation in the universe as a whole follows a more consistent pattern but also implies some form of larger scale finite or cyclic process.

Re-ionization is known to follow a twin peak anisotropic trend, which is a similar pattern to those of mass growth and morphology. Dixon, Furleanetto and Mesinger (2013) [¹⁴] found He-II fluctuations in 'optical depth' peaking of order of magnitude scales in the epoch around $z \sim 2$. Fontanot et al (2014) [¹⁵] also confirm the relevance of the background re-ionization contribution of quasars at $z < \sim 3$. Re-ionization is a well known effect of quasar activity and the quasar eras coincide at least loosely with the peak $> z \sim 6$ hydrogen (and $< z \sim 3$ Helium) re-ionisations.

2.1 Population distribution

We consider the TPD's of strong quasars and galaxy morphologies and of various peculiar patterns. The late quasar era peak in activity and profile each side of $z \sim 1.7$ is shown in Figure 1, based on SDSS-DR4 data. There are an estimated 3,000 'strong quasars' in the main SDSS sample of 46,000, which correlates with observationally estimated 3-7 per cent of galaxy population. At $z \sim 1.7$ quasar population peaks at $\sim 2,000$ from a base of a few hundred preceding the narrow ($z \sim 2.8$) stellar locus obscuration zone. An unexplained plateau appears at $z \sim 0.5 < 0.9$ before declining to the near universe. (Note; the apparent final collapse is a distortion). The rise to the peak corresponds with the well known but not yet understood major reduction in fraction of passive red galaxies. In a corresponding trend both Hershel and CANDELS data show that particularly low-luminosity AGN's are vanishing by $z \sim 2$. Some kind of major 'reverse' evolution of morphologies from red to blue is implied which correlates to the second quasar era.

Figure 1: Quasar population distribution for redshift $z = 1 < z < 4$ from the 46,000 SDSS DR4 (2QZ) sample. The late 'Quasar Era' peaks at $z \sim 1.7$. Note the stellar locus at $z \sim 2.8$ does not distort the data. See also Richards et al. (2002). P. Jackson.

In the early universe, the HST Ultra Deep Field survey and data confirm similar $z \sim 6$ galaxy morphologies to now, except that each corresponding version is significantly smaller and of lower mass. Evolution after $z \sim 6$ seems to more closely match expectation as spiral fraction gives way to discs and stellar populations evolve from blue towards red (after correction for cosmic redshift). At $z = 1.2 > z = 0.2$, following the second quasar era peak, the (22,051) ALHAMBRA survey

data suggests an evolutionary tendency with similarities to the the inter-era sequence from gradually tightening spiral forms blending into discs with reddening of the original stellar populations.

2.2 Luminosity

Evolution of luminosity between morphologies and reducing redshift has its own independent cycle. The cyclic model is consistent with the observed peculiar patterns and stellar distribution from two main sources, both related to relative velocity and ionization. Orbital velocity rate varies most severely near virial radii, which may account for the higher production in these zones. More particularly in later morphologies lobe growth in bulges from early outflow activity will account for concentrated mass and velocity deltas at the lobe surface. The lobe surface expands due to the pressure differential. The spread of re-ionized matter forming the membrane is analogous to the holographic principle, where the 'information' from the previous iteration of the galaxy is embedded and spread across the expanding membrane. The lobes will then tend to concentrate high luminosity centrally within red disc galaxies.

Local halo luminosity would correlate with maximum rotational velocity which we assume may be well before mid cycle. An open spiral may then not meet the Tully-Fisher mass/velocity relation. The *ATLAS^{3D}* and other kinetic surveys may find such a new correlation if focused on open spiral forms. Bulge luminosity will be a marker of the evolution of jet energy and lobe growth, but the sporadic jetting also occasionally found will sustain significant error bars. Superluminal jets are now well understood as a source of gamma ray bursts (GRB's), while sub-relativistic outflow 'winds' have been identified as a fairly distinct mode (Sadoowski et al. 2013) [16] at lower AGN spin rates. We assume that outflow winds build up into jets from increasing spin rate. Sadowski obtains empirical formula for jet power and momentum in excess of accretion rate. We discuss a cause for this excess below. Arav et al (2013) [17] find robust values for outflow mass flux and kinetic luminosity at quasar HE0238-1904 of $40 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and 1045 erg s^{-1} , respectively, the latter a significant ~ 1 per cent of the bolometric luminosity, indicating a very significant mechanism at work.

2.3 Growth of mass and size

The anisotropic growth 'steps' temporally focused around the quasar era's are suggested as significant and a key falsification of our model. Outflow mass volumes have been found higher than disc accretion, including by Bolatto et al, (2013), [18] supporting the model of AGN and jet ionization of new matter along with re-ionization of old. Ionization mechanisms are discussed below. Outflow delays are evident in a small number of cases. The focusing of accretion without outflows then forms the small population of ring galaxies.

The contribution to mass and scale growth from quasar 'disc recycling' is a proposition which requires investigation and quantification. The anisotropy of growth rates giving the peaks found in the early and local universe appears to be problematic for assumptions of mass growth due to mergers alone, which may be expected to be isotropically distributed over time. From significantly larger data sets over the last few decades, no conclusive evidence of actual mergers has emerged beyond the moderate level consistent with the 'irregular' morphologies which are generally agreed as in the order of $> \sim 8\%$. The proposed model then suggests and predicts that the recycling process will be

shown to make a greater contribution to observed growth of mass and size including halo plasma and gas, than that arising from mergers. (See also 4.2).

2.4 Dwarf satellites and halo rotation

The dwarf galaxy population is almost entirely made up of satellites within haloes. Satellite density may be consistent locally but appears to reduce at higher z . The apparent fall off in numbers is generally attributed to observational constraints. We will suggest in section 6 that the dwarf satellite population has built up since the early universe, and that the increase will be found to have been focused at the quasar eras. A solution for the long problematic 'core-cusp' simulation problem then emerges, predicting the flat CDM distributions found.

Both halo and satellite galaxy orbits tend to be significantly kinetically decoupled from the disc, with often close to perpendicular halo rotation (Davis et al, 2001). [10] Halo's generally have different orbits to the satellites they contain. No consistent explanation of satellite formation or the commonly found halo kinematic decoupling have been found. Our model includes a single cause for both effects, which we derived below. A staged evolution of average halo /disc decoupling angles and redshift is also predicted, with greater orbital angle differences following the quasar eras.

2.5 Chemical evolution

Micali, Matteucci and Romano (2013) [2] found that to successfully reproduce the chemical evolution of the stellar population of the Milky Way, three main infall episodes are suggested with short timescale thick and thin disc formation. The first event may last ~ 0.4 Gyr with later time scales increasing, the last mass accretion taking ~ 6.0 Gyr. Metallicity distribution is then well reproduced, but a remaining problem is that the thick disc must have formed independently from the halo. Our model mechanism varies but produces both the independently formed thick disc and the multiple 'inflows' which we identify as full accretion events. The results of our cycle are then consistent with the peculiar chemical evolution pattern found by Micali, and corresponding stellar age distributions.

The first of the three infalls proposed by Micali did not initially emerge from our model. Early universe data is scarce, but an early first cyclic event is not precluded. A study of the Perseus cluster reveals Iron and other heavy elements already widely dispersed when the cluster started to form (Werner et al. 2013) [19] implying dense supernova and high AGN outflow activity; “*between about 10 and 12 billion years ago*”. Werner's finding supports the possibility of significant late universe slowing of early rapid cycle periods.

2.6 Bars

No longer considered as a feature peculiar only to spirals bars have been found as ubiquitous to most galaxy morphologies. While more familiar in blue galaxies strong bars have now been identified in visual Galaxy Zoo analysis i.e. Hoyle et al. (2011) [7] in ~75-80% of redder galaxies. Analysis of bar lengths and populations in local discs has brought no new insights on formation or evolution. Various theories are proposed for bar formation and dynamics, including acting as a channel from disc arms to bulge, and vice versa, but none are confirmed, and no kinematic evidence of significant longitudinal flow is found. Galaxy bars have remained enigmatic.

Some apparent but unresolved structure has been detected. Bar ends are always at the root of spiral arms and at the main virial radius and rotational velocity step, where the central zone rotates in 'lockstep' and faster than the arms. The centre section of bars merge into the bulge. Our new model very simply derives bars from the residue of re-ionized jet outflow matter via the coherent mechanism described below. We predict a steady recent increase in total bar population (from $z=1.7$) linked to quasar activity (see Fig. 1).

3 Intrinsic Rotation and Virial Radius.

All matter in the quantum vacuum is subject to an effect termed 'spontaneous intrinsic rotation' (SIR) described in Parra, Barnes and Catto, (2011), [20] Parra, Barnes, Calvo, Catto (2012), [21] and Barnes et al. (2013). [22] The intrinsic rotation may be of a body or of a more loosely bound discrete inertial system within a larger field. The cause is poorly understood, but the result is considered to be a *gyrokinetic* effect. The rotation acts on the major

axis of the system. If the system's components are loosely bound, the effect is then on a primary virial radius r_v . See also Romanelli & Kamendje (2009) [23] and Wang et al. (2011). [24] There is commonly more than one radial velocity step in spiral galaxies, of unknown cause but likely to relate to mass distribution. The steps are often less well defined so less 'steep' in discs. The principle r_v includes the bar and surrounding plasma and gas, rotating in bodily 'lock-step', so largely conserving a slightly 'flattened' bar form and long axis. In virial theory of galaxy rotation, anisotropic velocity gradients beyond the principal virial radius smooth out, but the velocity step pattern has an apparently wide radial distribution. Virial radii are quantitatively shown by Kravtsov (2013) [25] to have a near linear relation to galaxy size. Kinetic analysis is difficult without a temporal sequential basis, but no coherent evolution of morphology has yet emerges from increasingly detailed surveys.

We propose that velocity steps at virial radii may migrate radially, initially expanding then later falling inwards to the bulge due to accretion. Bar lengths may then first grow then contract as the bars blend into bulges. The phenomena of intrinsic rotation provides the power of our model we now present, both as the driving force of galaxy rotation and of the AGN itself, which gains high orbital angular momentum (OAM) energy from the natural rotational tendency of matter. Consistent mechanisms for the coherent resolution of all the observed phenomena discussed above appear to emerge coherently from the new models cyclic dynamics.

4 The Cyclic Evolutionary Sequence

4.1 The missing link

An intuitive concept of secular galaxy evolution may be the tightening of spiral arms with increasing rotations, followed by blending into discs as described by Buta and Zhang (2010). [26] Average stellar age seems to quite closely accord with an evolution from blue spirals to reddened discs. Yet no such evolution of stellar population is apparent. Stellar age distribution complexity and incoherent correlation of luminosity, metallicity and other criteria cannot be consistently resolved alongside symmetrical evolution. The inward transfer of matter and OAM energy from discs to bulges is also a

popular conception. The inward flow concept extends to AGN accretion, feeding jet outflows. Matter is known to be drawn inwards from what is termed the 'accretion disc', but the extent of the disc is poorly understood and defined, as is what happens to the matter in the outflows which can extend thousands of light years into the outer halo. We find then that when considering peak AGN activity the 'loose ends' of secular evolution theory become more problematic.

It was clear that some form of feedback of jet matter was essential to resolve various issues, but no feedback mechanism has yet been verified. Ragone-Figueroa et al (2013) [27] identify that brightest cluster galaxy (BCG) structure and mass cannot be modelled by thermal feedback without larger scale outflows from BCG precursors with a “*more widespread effect over the galaxy volume*”. Our cyclic model offers the 'missing link', including retention of outflow matter but also predicting galaxy characteristics and the distribution of morphological populations found. The apparently fundamental secular evolutionary stages, of spiral to disc, and blue to red are inherent in our new iterative model as each naturally emerges from the cyclic dynamic mechanism. The missing link we propose is the extension of accretion and re-ionization to include the whole disc, the exhaustion of matter and angular momentum, and the accompanying formation of the outflow matter into a new open blue spiral on the new perpendicular axis. Inconsistencies with 'event horizons' and black hole firewalls are overcome by invoking Steven Hawking's chaotic information preservation referred below where the re-'radiation' is in the jet outflow.

4.2 Growth

The significant growth in mass and size of all galaxy types since the early universe has commonly been considered as arising only from mergers. We now suggest that significant growth may result from the ionization of new matter as a consequence of the AGN driven recycling process we describe. (Ionization and the AGN jet mechanisms are discussed in section 5 below). Mergers are a long established paradigm but confirmed population is sparse. Simulations of merger interactions cannot model or recover the symmetry of present galaxies. An underlying galaxy population density drop may also be expected from mergers but is not found. The major merger rate at $z \sim 1$ is so much lower than

assumed that Kaviraj et al (2011) [²⁸] propose minor infall mergers of satellites drive ETG star formation, but again with little evidence. Simmons et al (2013) [²⁹] conclude that mass growth is not from mergers. Debattista et al, (2013) [³⁰] find AGN growth also a result of '*secular processes*' not mergers. Kavejari et al, (2013) [³¹] show that mergers cannot produce the $z \sim 2$ star production peak and suggest that only $< \sim 15\%$ of galaxies may contain signatures of mergers.

Figure 2: Number density evolution of blue and red bias galaxies at redshifts $0.2 < z = 1.8$ in the combined COMBO-17+4 mid band survey (42,134) for min magnitude; $MB < -21.0$. The pre $z=2$ red dominance of total population changes to give a blue peak then an evolution back to red. (Note; growth in size levels out from $z \sim 1.5 > z = 0$.) Smoothed curve shown. Data points also shown from M. Jaeger. (thesis) 2013 Fig. 6.11b.

After the phase dominated by passive red galaxies from $z=4 > 3$ there is an increase in luminosity and a significant 'quenching' population shift to a higher fraction of 'younger' blue spiral galaxies at $z \sim 2 > z \sim 1.5$. The population then seems to evolve steadily back towards redder bias and more blended discs. Figure 2 drawn from the COMBO 17+4 mid-band 42,134 galaxy survey shows significant shifts to blue dominance from $\sim z = 1.8$ evolving back to red from $z \sim 1.3$ (data points shown are from Jaeger (2013). [³²] Such peculiar evolution correlates strongly with a mechanism regenerating many older red galaxies into young spirals during the most recent quasar

eras identified. The increasing disc luminosity is assigned to the outflows and lobes. Brodwin et al (2013) [³³] have discovered a loosely corresponding collapse of cluster star formation rates from the Spitzer/IRAC Shallow Cluster Survey at $z \sim 1.4$. The timing of such recycling would be expected to have a

normal Gaussian distribution between quasar eras. The fewer old red discs in the local universe are likely to have high central luminosity as the lobes and bulge grow. Mergers will likely continue to contribute an unknown fraction to mass growth but our cyclic model appears able to produce most of the increases in mass and size found consistent with the ~95% symmetry observed and the apparently consistent overall galaxy number density $z=3 > z=0$.

The 'matter recycling' mechanism can provide the missing link between old red lenticular galaxies and young blue open spirals to complete eternal iterative recycling. Colouration is taken as a valid indicator of age, but many old stars in the bulge and greater oblate spheroid halo will escape recycling. Small populations of very old stars would then remain in local spirals at $z < 1.7$ mainly populating the halo margins. Older stars near the core will be the result of lobe growth formation from early outflow activity. Our model predicts that very few old stars should end up in or migrate to the spiral arms.

4.3 Bar Formation

Perhaps the most perplexing feature of galaxies, the central bar feature emerges from the new model as the natural consequence of the opposing outflows of matter. The outflows contain all accreted disc matter, but outflows stop when the 'fuel' of disc OAM is exhausted. The re-ionized matter will then form two dense columns, the inner parts of which would be preserved within the virial radius to form the bar. Bars may then be merely evolutionary artifacts with little more part to play during the main cycle. Bar length will first depend on the virial radius then later on bulge accretion. As jet cone opening angles vary widely so will the length and definition of bars. A cylindrical density gradient would evolve into an elliptical cross section due to rotation on the longitudinal axis with the new disc. The inner bar and outer trailing arms may then retain internal evidence of the helical dynamics of their progenitor jet. Motions of stars should be found to have a residual orbital component within the arms bulk flow rest frame. New stellar production will be highest at the outer bar end and also at the leading edge of fast rotating bars, commensurate with the high local orbital velocities relative to the halo gas rest frame. Figure 3a shows 'Centaurus A' in mid recycling with strong ~15,000yr long jets. On

full disc accretion and ejection the virial central section of the recycled column of matter starts rotation on the perpendicular axis (3b). Less than one rotation then produces the familiar open barred spiral morphology shown in figure 3c.

Figure 3:a) Left; Centaurus A. NGC 5128. Twin jets distribute re-ionized disc matter and gas in a spiral. The outer ring is last to be accreted. b) Centre. When the old disc matter is consumed the column of re-ionized matter and gas created by the jets starts to rotate on a new axis perpendicular to the old disc plane. (see also below) c) Right; NGC1300. Rotational velocity increases at a virial radius on the new axis forming an open spiral with a bar. Peak ionization and star formation is at the high shear zone of the bar tips 'feeding' the spiral arms which rotate with the typical radial velocity gradient. NASA FSA

Spiral galaxies will be formed from two pairs of arms, one from each end of the bar. The twinned arms result from spiral distribution of jet matter giving a cone or cylinder which then naturally resolves into a distinct *pair* of trailing arms when the rotated on the perpendicular axis with a radial velocity gradient. The four MW arms are confirmed by Urquhart et al (2013). [³⁴] Matter from outflow asymmetries will then resolve into 'partial' or 'broken' spiral arms. Our sun is on one such discontinuous arm section. Jet cone opening angles may commonly be only be a few degrees but also wider than 45° in which case the arms would be indistinct. Wide angles create the oblate spheroids and great ionized gas clouds which are linked to 'AGN shutdowns' (Keel et al, 2012). [³⁵] Our model is consistent with the general GZ bar size and morphology analysis (Hoyle 2011) [7] and predicts the localized overpopulation of longitudinal 'post

jetting' columnar galaxy mass forms in the region $z=2 > z=1$. Elongated forms are easily mistaken for 'edge on' discs, but will quickly start rotating driven by the concentrated 'bar' mass, so evolving into the increasingly 'S' shaped forms. Bars become clearly defined and symmetric about the centre of mass during evolution through this 'open spiral stage'. An over-population of open spirals is then predicted by the new model at $z \sim 1.5$. The peculiar population evolution profile shown in Figure 2 is consistent with our model's prediction of a blue excess at that era, and also a constant total galaxy population level.

A multi-stage formation history consistent with our model is implied by the finding of Petty et al (2013) [36] of nearby Hubble 'early type' galaxies observed in the mid-infrared by WISE and GALEX imaging. Some evidence suggests that the cycle period between such stages may be increasing. If the Milky Way recycled late in the $z \sim 1.7$ quasar era, then principal disc stellar age may be 6-8Gyr, which correlates with most findings. The older stars would largely populate the core and halo. If the average remaining lifetime of current disc star has any correlation with recycling, which cannot be assumed, then an increasing cycle period may perhaps be suggested of $\sim 12-14$ Gyr. A 10Gyr cycle period between past quasar eras was estimated by Martini and Weinberg (2001) [1] with short active quasar lifetimes. The current conceptual toy model stage can only approximate and identify areas for more detailed investigation. Predictions cannot then be quantitatively defined beyond firm trends as more detailed population data is required. Required data may now be identified and should be available within the next few years subject to prioritization.

4.4 AGN Death

The AGN only exists at all through orbital angular momentum. In our model the nucleus then 'dies' once the matter that constitutes the dynamic energy is exhausted. The new axis of rotation and OAM then forms and grows a new active nucleus. Building rotational velocity then slowly rebuilds the bulge size and energy from accretion of matter and OAM from the new arms and disc. At low energies complete stars may be accreted and ejected. Fourteen recent cases of such 'hypervelocity' stars have been identified leaving the Milky Way disc on the perpendicular axis. The ubiquitous EM toroidal morphology is extended

to the whole AGN dynamic structure. We explain below how this form produces the acceleration of matter into the outflows and jets. The toroidal morphology is often screened by bulge 'dust' and gas, but the dust itself usually takes on the toroidal form. The growing and luminous cocoon 'lobes' formed by the spiralling outflows on the toroid axis are usually detectable through the bulge matter before the breakout of the high powered jets. We propose that the high local star production at the lobe surfaces in the lenticular phase is promoted by the high relative speed of outflows in the ambient medium which increases ionization rates and total local mass. We discuss the ionization process further in part 5. The lobes expand with growing AGN energy until the jets burst out as collimated flows. The outpouring of ionized matter reaches into and often through the old halo, forming the now oblate spheroid perpendicular to the disc plane. The most powerful outflows would then propagate the great ionized gas clouds commonly found.

4.5 Rings and Peanuts

Ring galaxies such as the Cartwheel and Hoag's object result from 'inside out' accretion and late jetting. The Cartwheel, not resulting from an 'explosion', has a flat ring and strong ring to core *tangential* accretion trails. Anisotropic accretion is also found at NGC 7213 (Schnorr-Muller et al 2014) [37] with two spiralling Doppler shifted strands detected at $<200\text{kms}^{-1}$. There are 12 'polar ring' galaxies which we attribute old disc remnants from late lenticular or 'SO' stage prior to jetting. Bulge luminosity is from the lobes. We consider toroidal EM fields as twin opposing vortices joined at the neck with outer field 'lines' returning to 'close' the torus. Orientation of electron spin axis in EM fields aligns with the core structure, a fact which we find important in analysing the effects of interactions. The same spin alignments have been confirmed in dark matter haloes and filaments. (Aragon-Calvo, Yang, 2014) [38] in the hierarchy implicit in discrete field dynamics. Li, Morris and Baganoff (2013) [39] show the Milky Way AGN parallel to the disc axis with parsec scale perpendicular outflows from the axis. Torus/disc plane alignment appears to be ubiquitous. Observed from the disc a torus may have a 'boxy' form however, the twin lobes on the bar axis will also give the 'peanut' appearance. Quillen et al (2013) [40] find inner bar 'buckling' forcing orbiting stars to undergo “*vertical resonances*”

consistent with lobe over-densities. The older stellar populations found near galactic centres are then explained as formed from the early outflows lobes.

Figure 4 shows the proposed full evolutionary cycle from quasar re-ionization and birth of a new AGN on the new perpendicular axis at '0 hours'. The inner ring shows typical high-z galaxies. The outer ring uses more recent examples.

Figure 4: Proposed Cyclic model of secular galaxy evolution. The inner ring shows the smaller and low mass early universe version of each morphology. New cycles start at 0 hrs on a new perpendicular axis with increased size and mass due to ionization. Indicators suggest 3-4 full cycles over the last ~13Gyr. and a slowing cycle period of ~10-12Gyr (last quasar peak; $z \sim 1.7$). Credit; P. Jackson. Images; NASA/ESA.

The scales shown are indicative of relative size over cosmic time, so also of growth in mass, and the similar range of morphologies within what we identify as previous cycles. Any evidence of significant feed-back flow from the jet to the original disc plane axis will falsify the proposed model, as would the confirmation of a higher merger population than presently conclusively confirmed. The model predicts that neither will be confirmed.

Table 1 schedules and describes the basic stages of evolution and also shows the Hubble 'tuning fork' sequence classification codes. Irregulars, globular clusters and dwarf satellites are discussed below and outside the primary sequence. We anticipate difficulties in comparisons between our cyclic model and the familiar Hubble classifications. The Hubble 'sequence' designates

Stage.	Characteristics	Cyclic Evolution Model.
1 (SBd)	Open, straight luminous arms, rotation starts to virial radii.	
2. (SBc)	Core and bar rotation trails & propagates two pairs of arms.	
3. (SBb)	Open Spiral. Peak speed at bar tip promotes star formation.	
4. (SBa)	Arms extend & tighten, radial velocity gradients established.	
5. (Sa/b)	Bar more hidden, arms tighter and starting to blend.	
6. (Sb/c)	Arms well blended, core builds, new weak bipolar outflows.	
7. (Sc)	Arms now a disc AGN spin and bulge accretion increasing.	
8. (E)	Disc stars ageing, outflows form 2 growing bright lobes.	
9. (E/SO)	Disc reddening, mass focusing, outflow/ jet power building.	
10 (So)	Lenticular. Fast accretion to bulge, AGN peaks, stronger jets.	
11 (Ab)	Ring consumed, collimated pulsed jets apparently at over c'.	
12 (-)	Bare quasar. Bulge & disc matter re-ionised into jet arms.	

Table 1: Cyclic evolutionary sequence stages 1-12 and the comparable Hubble 'tuning fork' designations.

'early type' galaxies as the redder blended discs which appear quite late in our proposed evolutionary cycle. We suggest that it may then be helpful to employ

the new descriptions 'young' and 'old', or perhaps clock face numerals to allow consistent description of the new cycle from blue open spirals through to red discs, lenticulars and rings. The familiar morphological 'types' may then be more logically ordered in sequence of 'age' since the previous recycling. The Hershel reference survey of dust content in galaxies reveals an evolution following our proposed sequence (Cortese et al, 2014) [41] with high content in our blue 'young' phase following re-ionization activity evolving to more sparse gas content for older, redder disc galaxies.

The key 'missing link' stage between an old red lenticular or ring form and a new open blue spiral has been hiding in plain sight awaiting assignment. We identify NGC2110 in Orion as such a case which has been much studied but is shrouded in 'dust'. Observations with the Keck telescopes adaptive optics has allowed high resolution in the near infrared and detailed kinetic analysis of the outflows, toroidal core and high rates of star forming activity. Fig. 5 shows a composite image of NGC 2110 constructed by Durre and Mould (2014) 42 who describe the galaxy as lenticular, but find major deviations from simple core rotation consistent with bipolar outflows and precession. The 'ring' of luminous central clumps is proposed by the authors as gas shocked by and within high speed re-ionizing jet outflows similar to Centaurus A. Using the Kennicutt Tamblyn Congdon (1994) equation $0.26 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ is suggested giving a cluster age of a few million years. The data is then a good initial fit to our cyclic model. We predict that halo decoupling will be found in further studies (see below).

Figure 5: NGC2110. Composite view of an AGN with precessing outflows and high star forming activity around a toroidal core tilted $\sim 45^\circ$ towards line of sight. We interpret the form as stage 1 of the cycle; re-ionized disc matter evolving into a new open spiral on a new axis. Swinburne University of Technology.

5 Mechanism

5.1 Re-ionization and discrete field domains.

The high-energy mechanism producing the acceleration of accreted matter into jets is described as '*shrouded in mystery*' and '*not well understood*' (i.e. Kumar et al. 2014). [⁴³] Evidence from disparate sources suggests a likely process and mechanism consistent with recent findings which we invoke and describe here. We also consider the complex dynamics of the jet itself and the implications of process on observation. We then describe how the key elements of Einstein's postulates of Special Relativity (SR) can be recovered in all cases from apparent violation by the superluminal motion of jet core pulses many times higher than c . A more consistent view of how the observed speed of light may be rendered constant emerges from endowing 'inertial frames' with physical reality as local and relative 'states of motion' of matter. The re-ionization of accreted disc matter and the photo-ionization of new conjugate fermion pairs at frame boundary 'shear planes' from the Higgs field are suggested to be closely related mechanisms, resulting from accelerations.

The density of the fermions condensed is 'relative speed' dependent for good purpose. It must absorb energy at arbitrary relative speed across the shear plane and re-emit at c in each particle's local centre of mass rest frame to implement spontaneous localization to c . The scattering mechanism then provides a frame transformation limited by γ (minimum wavelength) to conserve local c . The extinction distance (of the old 'speed' as well as propagation direction) is, as convention, a function of dielectric particle density. Light will be constantly re-scattered to c locally on interaction, as is the case in all dielectric media. We are then proposing that jet collimation 'domain limit' plasma behaves as other dense dielectric medium. 'Superluminal' pulses measured trigonometrically from Earth are then no longer a theoretical problem for the SR propositions;

“Light is always propagated in empty space with a definite velocity c ...” and “The same laws of electrodynamics and optics will be valid for all frames of reference...,”

We must also consider that Einstein was well aware and wrote of remaining

issues in the common 'interpretation' of relativity and wrote in his 1952 paper;

“The entire theory of (special) relativity is contained within the postulates.”

Some new 'interpretation' is then required, but we suggest that the new view resolves rather than adds to related issues. Another apparent anomaly resolved is that the findings of superluminal jet pulses (discussed further below) consistently use the AGN source or local ambient medium rest frame as the datum. All jets however have opposing contraflows (often shifted well to the red where receding). Analysis has shrunk from addressing the theoretical problem of the apparent 'doubling' of relative transverse velocities arising from the 'rate of change of position', for which a solution lies beyond the prescribed interpretation of Special Relativity. By invoking scattering to local c in all local frame domains our 'discrete field' model avoids such theoretical problems.

We propose that the re-ionization of accreted disc matter occurs principally during acceleration on the typical tokamak handed helical contraflow pathways around the continuous tube of the toroidal AGN body. A Venturi 'z-pinch' discharge emission zone would follow the well established acceleration process of Helicon-Plasma Discharge (Wiebold 2009) [44] The helical dynamics of toroidal nuclear tokamaks are discussed in 5.2 below. Conversely the ionization of *new* matter may occur largely in the inner jets themselves. Suzuki-Vidal et al. (2013) [45] have successfully laboratory modelled a toroidal magnetic field emitting protons trapped in jets. The emissions appear to emerge from the pinched field on the axis. The cone then provides a further helical morphology and polarisation. Gabudza, Cantwell and Cawthorne (2013) [46] confirm the toroidal and helical magnetic field components via a Faraday rotation gradient across the extended jet of 3C 380 surviving to hundreds of parsecs from the AGN. Speed and helicity reduce with distance but high resilience to turbulent diffusion is found in helical fields (Bhat, Blackman, Subramanian 2014).[47] Collimation is the kinetic layering of flows as new matter is continuously injected anisotropically into the outflow stream. Eriodic jet injection velocities are separated by ballistic 'working surfaces', as described by Mendoza, Hidalgo, Olvera and Cabrera (2009). [48] The velocity difference creates shear 'hyper-surfaces' where accelerated matter meets the slower moving material from earlier outflows and then also the surrounding ambient medium.

Collimated flows and turbulent magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) mixing are familiar and generally accepted mechanisms, if not fully understood. The new model proposes significant additional conjugate fermion pair production at the shear surfaces for which we invoke the Higgs mechanism. The resultant condensed matter is identified as a principal source of the growth in galaxy mass discussed above. The small surfeit of surviving annihilation may evolve as commonly assumed to bosons and molecular gas, consistent with the concentration of the mass growth during the quasar eras identified by Cimatti (2012) [13]. The invoked creation of spin particles by 'vacuum friction' or '*viscous drag between moving plates*' was proposed by Paul Davies (2005) [⁴⁹] and is not inconsistent with the initial fermion spin of the Higgs process. The extended jets will then also contribute significantly to the consummate growth of ionized matter haloes.

The proposal of AGN driven 'phases' of mass increases is consistent with the apparent concentration of growth and rapid morphology evolution from red to blue co-incident with the quasar era's discussed above. Porciani et al, (2004) [⁵⁰] and Dixon et al, (2013) [14] have shown that all cosmic re-ionization can be accounted for by quasar activity. If early epoch quasars recycled hydrogen and the later epoch re-ionized helium, then evolution of quasar energy $z \sim 6 \gg z \sim 2$ is implied. The possibility of an earlier shorter cycle commencing when the universe was only ~ 0.5 Gyr old is supported by the Micali et al [2] findings of three significant 'infall' events.

5.2 Quasar Plasma

For convenience we use the general description 'plasma' for the re-ionized and newly ionized or 'condensed' jet and halo matter. Plasma is considered to represent $\sim 99.5\%$ of all matter, but space plasma remains largely poorly understood and varies widely in electron/positron/proton/ion constitution. In our cyclic model protons form much of the jet stream and ambient medium but may also evolve rapidly from fermion coupling. Kumar et al (2013) [⁵¹] have found that at peak energies the electron-positron rich jets have a substantial proton content ~ 27 per cent of electron number density. The halo medium is

commonly thought to have average ambient electron densities of hundreds/cm⁻³ peaking at $\sim 10^{23}$ /cm⁻³ when shocked. Prochaska et al (2014) [52] find significant IGM H_I densities of $\sim 10^{15} - 10^{17}$ cm⁻² at $z \sim 2.5$. One peculiar quality of plasma is it's almost zero electromagnetic (EM) profile (refractive index $n=1$) before evolving to the $n > 1$ of bound matter. Pure electron/positron proton plasma is then invisible spectroscopically, or 'dark' before binding and evolution to other particles, CO and molecular gas.

Instantaneous conjugate fermion or Cooper pair production becomes constrained as energy density peaks approaching the optical breakdown ('OB mode') plasma limit at $\sim 10^{22}$ /cm³. EM waves cannot propagate in OB mode plasma, having a non-linear asymptotic response to heating when approaching the minimum wavelength limit γ . The power curve of the mechanism when approaching OB mode matches the Lorentz factor which limits effective local propagation speed to c at each collimation hyper-surface. The effects of OB are as found on spacecraft re-entry into Earth's plasmasphere where EM wave penetration is blocked and excess energy is emitted at heat. The OB mechanism, a familiar effect in non-linear optics, will then implement the asymptotic limit at γ preventing Lorentz violation. The Lorentz factor then emerges from the minimum wavelength limit and OB mechanism when crossing the two-fluid shear zone of each matter system's local inertial rest frame boundary. The dense free electron propagation and scattering suggested is consistent with what are termed the 'virtual' electrons in the 'other' frame at two-fluid plasma shear surfaces, seen as the dynamic case of the normal 'double layer' charged plasma.

The constantly changing datum for local propagation speed c by 'transition zone' electron scattering is the fundamental new hypothesis of 'discrete field' dynamics, though rather more an 'assembly' and new interpretation of theory and findings than 'new' physics. The proposal is also consistent with findings from simultaneous ground and space based observations reported by Walsh et al (2014) [53] of active dynamics in Earth's dense plasmasphere, referring to the speed dependence of GPS signals on plasmasphere density as an aid to plasmaspheric mapping. Maxwell's near/far field transformation then

successfully describes the transformation at the shear surface crossing, up the relativistic OB mode limit at gamma. Aberle (2004) [54] derived an algorithm partially successful in solving the two-fluid case for the Maxwell equations.

The MHD two-fluid view of Akhiezer & Polovin (1956) [55] as the *electron-positron* relation is commonly used with the 3+1 SR equations of Zenitani et al. (2009). [56] We simply invoke the transition zone (TZ)/ high energy shear plane as the two-fluid frame interface with conjugate fermion pairs scattering to local c on both sides to recover SR, which will then generate the Doppler wavelength shifts found. Simple models of two-fluid outflows “*implicitly ignore the motion of scatterers relative to the fluid*” and identifies “*missing physics*” (Salem & Bryan 2014). [57] Hints of an upstream/downstream speed change across a TZ implemented by annihilation exist in the recent work of Barkov et al (2014) [58] using linear and Lagrangian approaches with robust results but recognising that ‘*a different approach will be required*’ to resolve the Lorentz force terms. We propose the local bulk proper $c' = c$ solution.

Contribution of space plasma to gravitational lensing has been identified by a number of authors, including in terms of the weak field approximation by Er and Mao (2013). [59] Gao (2013) [60] suggests that dark energy may be the quantum fluctuations ‘*of* spacetime’ rather than *in* spacetime. Such a rationale is consistent with dark matter as condensed fluctuations *in* spacetime. The proton mass is $0.938\text{GeV}/c^2 = 1.67 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg}$, which is near the estimated range for dark matter of $\sim 8.6\text{GeV}$. The coupling potential of plasma is high and *independent* of EM profile and dielectric constant/refractive index. Electrons also have a small gravitational mass and small notional size, so join with protons and potentially other unknown particles. There would appear then to be no theoretical constraint to a significant contribution to halo gravitational potential from ionized plasma from quasar jet activity. A recent study of inter galaxy/clusters void dark matter confirmed that the majority of DM follows the radial halo density profiles of the matter (Sutter et al 2014) [61] suggesting connections with AGN activity. We suggest that better understanding of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ fermions may expose a greater contribution to dark matter (Jackson, 2014). [62]

We discuss important very long baseline array (VLBA) confirmation of refractive light path curvature from plasma kinetics below. The influence of matter as a lensing medium is now ubiquitous but still theoretically anomalous. Our discrete field model overcomes any relativistic theoretical bar to its recognition by recognising the scattering to local c as well as the optical axis refraction. Jaronsznski and Kostrzewa-Rutkowska, (2014) [63] provide more recent important findings and analysis. In the DFM the electron/positron pairs modulate the local EM radiation to the local c , but most will be immediately annihilated by the familiar local cancellation of the electric charge across the Debye length. We propose that rapid charge cancellation is a valid description for all 'electron shocks', allowing each side of the shear plane to scatter to c . We also propose that scattering to c across the shear surface can produce the problematic 'electron heating' shock dynamics found, which are not presently interpreted as a transformation between inertial (mass) systems. We suggest that a dynamic appraisal against *Cluster* mission data may prove worthwhile.

Jet outflows are clumpy, which may correlate with accretion flow with a significant but unknown delay factor. From an Eddington scaled mass accretion rate sample <0.01 including IR background absorption from pair production Gardner and Done (2013) [64] find jet power correlates better with spin than accretion rate, with the highest spin ($a^* > 0.8$) black holes giving peak jet power. Predictions of standard AGN/bulge and halo mass ratios have been proved false by the Chandra targets NGC 4342 and 4291 (Bogdan et al 2012) [65] with black holes 10-35 times more massive than they should be and halo 'tidal stripping' unlikely. Our cyclic model requires no significant tidal stripping. The AGN mass excess emerges as a short term spin peak. Inertial mass due to spin then approximates 'SMBH' gravitational mass, but is *focused on the spin (disc) plane*, so has less effect on lobe and jet matter. The dynamic recycling model then suggests non-spherical SMBH gravitational potential.

The shear surfaces are then formed by the compression bow shocks of each dense matter jet pulse. When jets meet stellar heliospheres collimated two-fluid shocks have been found (Araudo et al 2013) [66] forming the heliosheath. Fluctuating pressure driven boundaries are consistent with analysis of

Voyager's findings at the heliopause (Quenby & Webber 2013). [67] We propose that the large position changes of Earth's plasmaspheric shock will also be found at a stellar scale, and that the visible bow shock of star LL Orionis localizes propagation speed to c in the nebula and star frames.

5.3 Scattering

The process of atomic scattering of blackbody photons by electrons is now familiar. Zdziarski, Pjanka (2013) [68] provide an accurate formulae for this “*very common astrophysical process.*” The scattering to c in the particle rest frame implements the equivalent of 'continuous spontaneous localization' (CSL), normally considered theoretically as a wavefunction collapse model (Canate, Perle, Sudarski, 2013). [69] EM wave propagation then remains relativistic across each hypersurface between collimated rest frames. Arav et al. (2013) [16] describe quasar outflows as UV absorption troughs blueshifted with respect to the AGN's rest-frame spectrum as the scattering mechanism would produce. Aksenov et al (2013) [70] refer to the Doppler interaction process as the '*Comptonization*' of photons from relativistic plasma outflows.

The shear surfaces create a two-fluid plasma model (see Shumlak et al, 2004) [71] but with propagation and scattering instantaneously to local c in each co-moving frame, consistent with general observations, and deriving the Doppler shifts found including relativistic contraction (forming the shell) and wave compression to γ . Hirota et al. (2014) [72] describe the same rapid optically thick but transparent plasma shell formation in terms of photospheric radiative transfer. The transparency of 'light' “*instantaneously created electron-proton-photon plasma*” (Bégué, Vereshchagin 2014 [73] produces the low EM profile which renders the medium 'dark' to spectroscopy. Snell's Law of refraction is recovered across the shear surface transition zone by the $\Delta c - c'$, giving the coherent local propagation speed c in both frames at each shear collimation (so *apparent* $>c$ pulse speed). Equivalent blueshift effects exist in non-linear optics and photonics where laser-electron scattering produces tunable X-rays. (Powers et al 2013). [74] Ionization of matter from light applicable at high intensity was shown by Ehrenstein (1997) [75] and in the Impulsive Stimulated Raman Scattering (ISRS) described by Higuchi, Tamara

and Kuwata-Gonomaki (2013) [76] characterised as the 'transfer of orbital angular momentum' from light to matter. Re-emission at c in local particle frames naturally shifts emissions from the receding jet 'reverse shocks' to the red to give the radio sources found. We propose that the problematic; 'boundaries in parameter space' of jets described by Polko, Meir, and Markoff (2014) [77] in terms of solutions; “*impossible to converge to the correct values*” converge on applying the local Δc parameter.

5.4 Aberration

Kinetic reverse refraction (KRR) from the lateral bulk flow of plasma in space consistent with the kinetic Sunyaev-Zeldovich effect was predicted by Cordes et al, (1986) [78] and Rickett and Coles (1988). [79] Importantly the resulting lensing effect of rotation of the optical axis of re-emitted light has been confirmed by findings from the VLBA (Pushkarev et al, 2013) [80] from the aberration of light passing through a laterally moving plasma cloud. We identify KRR as equivalent to stellar aberration, where the apparent source position displacement is 'ahead' of the dielectric medium path. Liberati (2013) [81] shows that theoretically speed c “*independent of the chosen reference system*” is “*both true and false*” so allowing an anomaly free interpretation of SR. We constrain Lorentz Invariance, or 'propagation at c ' as always 'Locally' true, giving a 'discrete field' relationship of inertial systems of matter in nominal states of relative motion, as described in Jackson, Minkowski (2012) [82] consistent with concepts in Cohen, Glashow (2006), [83] also Rothenstein (2007), [84] and Feigenbaum (2008). [85]

Pulse speeds above c may then be 'apparent' from time/angular displacement calculations but are only *relative*, not proper *propagation* speeds, which are locally modulated in the Higgs field. We describe further below how dynamic collimation surfaces as kinetic domain boundaries recover the SR postulates from superluminal jets in the DFM. The price the 'interpretation' of SR has to pay to resolve the anomaly is merely a constraint on the 'range of influence' of a moving body in modulating light speed to 'local' frame c . For a galaxy the domain boundary is the halo, for a star the heliopause, for a planet the ionosphere. At smaller scales it's Maxwell's near/far field TZ, and for a particle

the 'valance' electron. The concept is consistent with Einstein's characterisation that particles are not 'in' space but are 'spatially extended'. USNO Circular 179, (Kaplan, 2005) [86] followed from IAU 2000 resolutions and identified that “*the apparently familiar concept of the ecliptic plane has not yet been defined in the context of relativity resolutions. A consistent relativistic theory of Earth rotation is still some years away.*” The concept of local modulation at discrete field domain boundaries now suggest a coherent, logical and falsifiable solution.

6 Superluminal Motion

Apparent superluminal ($>c$) quasar jet pulse speeds were predicted by Martin Rees in 1966. Though theoretically problematic such $>c$ jet core pulses have been confirmed at increasing apparent speeds ever since. Meyer et al (2013) [87] using the HST have measured pulses in nearby M87's jets at $<\sim 8c$. The fastest, at $20c-46c$ have been found at blazar FSRQ PKS 1510-089. (Cabrera et al, 2013) [9]. The 'narrow angle' geometrical effect exaggerates speed, but has only a limited domain, of $\sim 19^\circ$ -at $6c$. (Junor, Biretta, Livio, 1999). [88] The popular 'Fireball' theory (Paczynski 1986), [89] (Goodman 1986), [90] developed the collimated model (Rees 1985), [91] (Rees & Meszaros 1994) [92] with shock front flows and multiple shear surfaces, also evolving to the 'Fireshell' model. Duffell and MacFadyen (2013) [93] identified that; “*So far, there is a lack of a simple, physically-motivated model for generic relativistic outflows whose opening angle is not imposed in an ad-hoc fashion.*” and they propose a 'Boosted Fireball' model.

We build on the past shear collimation work in constructing a physically motivated model of multiple collimated flows separated by dense plasma two-fluid shear surfaces, which may be consistently rationalised in relativistic terms. The physical processes involved in two-fluid interactions is poorly understood. Light propagation across the near/far field transition zone presently requires an assumption of 'virtual' electrons. The mechanism discuss above conserves propagation at c by scattering to c in the local dense plasma rest frames each side of the shear surface. The high electron densities $<\sim 10^{23}/\text{cm}^{-3}$ ensures a minimal 'extinction distance' (subject to wavelength), extinguishing

the old wavelength and speed. The assumption of c in the propagating medium rest frame is consistent with QED and normal dense dielectric medium cases in optical science. We also identify close links between our two-fluid model and the complex science of surface and 'volume' plasmons, phonons, polaritons and (bound pair) excitons, and propose that dynamic refractive plane experiments will be able to falsify our model.

Only *real* electrons are required, and other theoretical assumptions are constrained [see 64-68]. The implications of local moving propagation media are consistent with the Friedman equations of change to vacuum permittivity, affecting cosmic redshift, but here the change is concentrated at the local high density shocks which form the shear planes. Speed c in the local frame is then conserved between interactions as a result of particle interactions themselves, as found in all dielectric media including those surrounding Earth. However, the change of position of the core emitting pulse can still be found as a rate of change of position. The relative progress found does not represent the 'Propagation Speed' specified and limited by the SR postulates. The speed found is then in a different category, representing arbitrary 'apparent' or 'co-ordinate' speed with respect to the arbitrary frames of distant inertial systems of matter. Local propagation speed c is conserved on shear surface transition by the delta wavelength λ instead of frequency change (for a fixed observer frame). The linear case is;

$$\lambda_c = \lambda_{c+v} (1 + v/c)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

The wave equation itself is invariant on transformation in Euclidean space, so the scattered wave is;

$$\psi' = \psi'_0 \sin 2\pi(f't' + 1/\lambda' x') \quad (2)$$

The propagation speed in the new fluid frame in the case of linearly converging inertial system rest frames is then;

$$f'\lambda' = \{f(1 + v/c)\} \{\lambda(1 + v/c)^{-1}\} = f\lambda = c \quad (3)$$

Local propagation speed c is thus conserved in all cases. The Rees, 'fireball'

and 'fireshell' concepts are then endowed with a physical mechanism consistent with the SR postulates. The mathematical model used for the common interpretation of SR may be improved to model the mechanism because '*Proper*' and '*Co-ordinate*' speed and 'time' acquire precise physical definitions. '*Proper*' equates to *propagation* involving interaction, while '*co-ordinate*' refers to an arbitrary 'apparent' position change rate from propagation at c in some other arbitrary moving dielectric. The light carrying signals *from* the moving emitter still always propagates at local c . The 'change of position', is equivalent to the apparently 'moving' shadow umbra on a curved surface, not limited by being a 'propagation speed'.

The Einstein and Maxwell equations require vacuum permittivity as a measure of field strength and a scalar function. Permittivity may be considered in terms of vacuum fluctuations, which may be considered as a measure of fermion pair or plasma particle content. The validity of this view is confirmed by the kinetic VLBA findings of Pushkarev discussed above. The implications of vacuum permittivity in Friedman's universe were identified by Sumner (1994), [94] who found that making no allowance for photon interaction effects would imply a rapidly contracting universe. Our cyclic model does not support a 'no interaction' scenario and agrees but constrains expansion.

We do not here discuss the choice of Compton or Raman (inelastic) scattering which seems to have small first order consequence. The scattering mechanism we invoke is consistent with the Compton scattering principles and formulas found by Zdziarski & Pjanka (2013) [67], not only at large scales, but consistent with local peculiar and major fluctuations of ion density. EM emissions, as photons *or waves*, *from* fast moving jet inner pulses are scattered to the local speed c of the new downstream system rest frame across the shear surface. The high Doppler shifts to gamma produced are found as GRB's (Mundell et al 2013) [95] as the precessing jets sweep across Earth's vector. Emissions received by a distant observer are at local proper speed c . The angular position change rate of the jet core pulse viewed from Earth only indicates "*apparent*" superluminal motion of the pulse not a local propagation speed. The proposed mechanism will be unfamiliar but has been found to

provide the required relativistic rationalisation identified by the IAU and USNO Circular 179 (Kaplan, 2005) [85] referred above. Consequential resolution of a number of related anomalous findings is implicit and will be discussed in further papers. The proposed new mechanism is then confirmed as worthy of more detailed investigation and falsification.

In nuclear (fusion accelerator) 'tokamaks', chaotic flow within the 'tubular' torus self-organizes into helical 'windings', which accelerates ionizing flows. Such self-organization may appear to violate the 2nd law of thermodynamics, but the fluid flow provides the recycling mechanism which allows entropy to also assume a cyclic so eternal validity. Helical dynamics, common in plasmas as Birkland currents, are now ubiquitous in optical science as OAM. The same helical dynamic is found in so called 'neutron stars' (Ciolfi and Rezzolla 2013). [96] Internal jet Faraday Rotation/B-mode polarisation from magnetic field 'twist' is found (O'Sullivan et al, 2013) [97] as circular polarisation of CMBR photons. Our model implies OAM (helicity) at all scales in EM radiation.

The velocity steps and two-fluid plasma mechanism at shear 'hyper-surfaces' typifies 'avalanche-ionization' (Chin, 2010) [98] (Polynkin et al, 2012) [99] where Kelvin–Helmholtz unstable mixing occurs as each new bulk flow moves hierarchically within previous decelerating flows. As jet matter slows and 'flares' due to ambient medium interactions the mixing dynamics and conical collimation (Laing, Bridle 2013) [100] behave very much like those familiar at Earth's ionospheric bow shock. Reodiger et al (2013) [101] identify that transport coefficients in highly ionized plasmas, considered as two inviscid incompressible fluids, are still ill-constrained. Sadowski et al (2013) [16] find a 'standard' empirical formula consistent with the popular Blandford-Znajek (1977) [102] model of jets powered by strong rotating magnetic field lines with a radial component, giving;

$$P = B^2 (r/r_c)^4 r_c c = B^2 r^4 \omega^2 / c \quad (4)$$

where r_c is speed of light radius B ; *polar* magnetic field strength, and ω angular velocity, providing a useful general approximation of power. We propose that greater non-linearity is likely as peak power is approached, but much further

work is required in this area. For the actual accelerating mechanism we invoke the poloidal 'loop' of magnetic flux forming paths of accreted matter with helical threading of the torus in handed co-rotating contraflows to a final magnetic field contraflow pinch point, equivalent to a theoretical 'singularity'. The pitch of the helix may be critical, as currently being found in super-conductor tokamak cable design (Arend Nijhuis, University of Twente). Accretion power is suggested as due to the normal vortex speed/pressure gradient function. The torus as a twin vortex is then conceptually the OAM powered 'engine' of the process, building the speed which re-ionizes the matter to create the initially proton rich jet. Much is still to be understood, but dynamic similarities between AGN's and nuclear tokamaks also appear to deserve more detailed investigation.

7 Kinematic Axis Decoupling

7.1 AGN, disc and halo

Kinematic Decoupling of core or halo rotational axis and disc angular momentum is commonly found but has remained highly anomalous (Davis et al, 2010 [10], (Cappellari et al, 2007), [103] (Hernandes-Monteagudo and Ho, 2009). [104] Decoupling is an important natural consequence of our cyclic model as the new spiral plane is close to perpendicular to the old plane. Halo rotation is often somewhat perpendicular to the galactic plane but may commonly be $>40^\circ$ from the main disc axis. Decoupling is also often triaxial (Cappellari, 2007) [102], which may then be a kinetic artifact of earlier events. SAURON kinetic survey findings confirm that halo and disc rotational axis decoupling is ubiquitous, but may 'fade' after a few Gyr as asymmetry is reduced. The population fraction of co-rotating gas rich haloes increases over cosmic time, including (Biffi and Maio 2013) [105] evolving from a few percent at $z \sim 20$ to $\sim 5-15\%$ by $z \sim 9$. The $z \sim 20 < 9$ pattern would be consistent with shorter early universe quasar era cycles. A recent limited survey of nearby SO galaxy 'ionized-gas' haloes found $\sim 71\%$ with a “*visible counterrotation of the ionized-gas component with respect to the stellar component.*” (Kacsov, Sil'chenko, Afanasiev 2013). [106] In our new model, the old outer halo orbital angular momentum initially retains the old axis. The 'jet head' clusters will then be 'dragged' by halo rotation towards the old axis. We predict that the drag

produces the complex dwarf satellite orbital planes between disc and halo. Bulk motion of systems through the ambient frame would also have the potential to contribute to orbital anisotropies.

Typical peculiar galaxy velocities in local group rest frames may be ~ 100 kps (Peebles, Phelps, Shaya and Tully, 2001). ^[107] Opposing age-matched satellite galaxies may then have growing asymmetries, leaving the youngest as the most symmetrical. McDermid and Peltier (2007) ^[108] identify two 'types' of decoupling in an OASIS integral-field spectrograph sample of 28 'elliptical' and lenticular galaxies. The main kiloparsec scale halo decoupling from the disc and at the core of the bulge is found by Rees and Zijlstra (2013) ^[109] consistent with other Sgr.A. Indicators. Wide scatter of all characteristics seems common. Some jetting is stop-start with apparent axis changes between outflows. More detailed investigational work is needed in this area. No other integrated mechanism has been shown to derive kinematic halo decoupling, however our toy model is not presently able to describe many other effects including AGN instabilities such as the apparent core-disc decoupling. We also find that no classification system or simulation has proved able to rationalise or reproduce evolutionary processes between morphologies and observed properties and dynamics including most orbital decoupling (Capellari et al, 2007) [90], (Debattista et al, 2013) [30].

The long range rotation of polarization plane alongside but independent of Faraday rotation will include the birefringence found during the extinction process, all as first confirmed by Nodland and Ralston (1997). ^[110] The implied scattering to local c of the halo plasma and gas virial rest frame is not yet fully theoretically integrated but can be consistently considered in terms of the kinetic classification produced by Emsellem et al (2007; 2011) ^[111] ^[112] in the parameter;

$$\lambda_R \equiv (R/V)/(R\sqrt{V^2 + \sigma^2}). \quad (5)$$

In April 2013 the NASA Fermi probe seemed to confirm the 2005 MAGIC findings of 10^3 second delays between low and high energy radiation at GRB 130427A. Amelino-Camelia et al (2013) ^[113] find evidence of both QV

coupling and intrinsic GRB properties in the soft spectral lags. All such kinetic effects have previously suffered from problematic theoretical rationalizations which may now prove resolvable. The other main 'new' component of our model is that quasar jets continue until the AGN is starved of fuel, then starting a new cycle. Evolution from open blue spiral to red disc and lenticular is ubiquitous as assumed. A secondary decoupling predicted by our model is of the helical motion of the jet cylinders retained as a kinetic anisotropy within the galaxy spiral arms once part of the new disc plane perpendicular to the column major axis. Adjacent arms, including the twinned 'column wall' components from the ends of each bar, should retain some components of stellar velocity perpendicular to the galactic plane and also in opposing 'orbital' directions, producing 'wave-like' motions. Such a dynamic pattern has been identified and reported by Williams et al (3013). [¹¹⁴]

7.2 Dwarf Satellites

The modelling of satellite galaxy formation and evolution is famously problematic. Orbital decoupling does not follow halo kinetics so other mechanisms must contribute. Shaya and Tulley (2013) [¹¹⁵] identify that confinement of Local Group (LG) satellites to thin planes “*presents a challenge to the theory of hierarchical galaxy clustering.*” Greater correlations in the LG are invoked by Tulley, but no consistent mechanism beyond the break up of cosmic sheets to filaments is found. Dwarf satellite orbital anisotropies include the long debated Holmberg effect of galaxies where group orbital anisotropy is apparently conserved (Knebe et al, 2004). [¹¹⁶] Simulations cannot produce the non-cuspy core common to many satellites, termed the *core-cusp problem* (Ogiya, Mori, 2011). [¹¹⁷]

In our cyclic model the jet head mass 'pile ups' would have to evolve to form bodies which would have a dense but flat plasma distribution and no cuspy core. The Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC) has an unexplained principal age limit at $\sim >7\text{Gyr}$. The matter 'piled up' in the jet heads would result in dense nodules at $\sim 150,000 < 300,000\text{lyr}$ radius. The SMC $\sim 163,000\text{lyrs}$ away appears to have been almost entirely formed at $z \sim 1.5$ and terminates the hydrogen rich 'Magellanic stream', which our process suggests is the ionized outflow residue.

Some older outflow and halo stars will always be bound up in the jets, and low level production also continue. Coignoni et al (2013) [¹¹⁸] find star formation rate 0.5-2 degrees from the SMC centre increased by < 3 times 5-7 Gyr ago.

The Milky Way globular cluster NGC 2417 is unusually dispersed for the stellar mass contained. Cohen & Kirby (2012) [82] conclude that no nucleosynthetic source is capable of explaining the chemical makeup. Belokurov et al (2013) [¹¹⁹] identify its position; central to the Sagittarius (Sgr) remnant trailing and precessing stream, and at ~100kpc distance. Circumstantial evidence for globular cluster formation by jets can be commonly found. The Milky Way's Ursa satellites are opposite to the SMC and share a common orbit decoupled from both disc and halo orbits. An orbital pole <~27° away is shared by Draco, Leo II and Fornax (Pawlowski, Groupa 2013) [¹²⁰] orbiting at ~240km s⁻¹. Ursa minor and Draco have 'single age' populations at ~11>10Gyr, which is roughly consistent with formation during early quasar era. As discussed in section 6 above, the satellites orbital plane is likely to be influenced by the halo rotation over time so evolve away from the disc plane.

The Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) also contains bar signatures and a younger fraction ~2Gyr, suggesting an active intermediate scale nucleus. Bland-Hawthorne et al (2013) [¹²¹] suggest an 'eruption' of the Milky Way's Sgr.A to form the stream and the LMC. Our model agrees. The LMC has greater mass and an identifiable nucleus, and so it may be that the younger population element stems from outflow activity of the galaxy's own AGN. Andromeda is orbited by a number of similar satellites with roughly opposing distributions. The Pan- Andromeda (PandAS) survey of M31 identifies streams including the 'giant stellar stream' and a total of 34 satellites including the 'south west cloud' at ~10⁷ M_⊙ and a number of dwarf spheroids. The intermittent jetting and wide cones found in some cases are likely to contribute to total globular satellite numbers. Some satellites have complex forms, suggesting other formation and evolutionary mechanisms may also be at work. Further detailed survey data is required to allow new patterns to be identified.

8 Fractal Dynamics

A paradigm of initial galaxy formation is of dark matter collapse to clumps which then merge, then rotate from some unidentified force. We've identified intrinsic rotation, but with no cause other than some dynamic QV asymmetry. We find all effects invoked and found to be consistent with a fractal model and possible longer term cyclic cosmology. Freidman's seminal 1922 paper identified that Einstein's GR is compatible with the framework of a cyclical universe and Freidman's own cosmology implies some cyclical dynamic. If the proposed galactic recycling process can be scaled up to universal size, it would not rely on either isotropy or the homogeneity of Bianchi models. None the less a scaled up cyclic model would appear directly able to conceptually derive each of the peculiar anisotropies of the CMBR identified by Cobe, WMAP and Planck surveys. Such anisotropies included Helicity, axial flow, lateral and other asymmetries and the 'cold spot' found. Relativity predicts that all black holes at all scales will behave the same. No limit to scale is identified. Markov et al (2013) [¹²²] have confirmed scaling with mass as found with the high feed rates at the 70 million solar mass M81 AGN. The evolution of galactic dust content from high to low discussed above (Cortese et al) [⁴¹] is repeated at the cosmic scale with the evolution of the dark fluid equation of state from dark matter abundance back towards dark energy since the early universe (Kuntz et al 2009) [¹²³] The suggested extension of the dynamic is highly speculative but consistent with the pattern found.

A cause of intrinsic rotation may itself emerge from the MHD flow patterns around the main bulk flow axis leading towards Centaurus. The gravitational basis of the original 'great attractor' designation is inconsistent with the flow pattern found, decreasing with distance each side of an axis. The dynamics are more consistent with an outflow. The 'great attractor' may then conceivably represent a scaled up version of a receding jet head viewed from Earth's frame rather than an accretion point. In either the accretion or outflow case a finitely recycling universe is implied by consistent logical analysis, perhaps within both a temporal and spatial multiverse. The 'Big Bang' might then be a temporally extended outflow leading to consistencies with a number of popular 'cyclic', 'bounce' and 'big crunch' cosmologies. The expanding and collapsing

'anthropic multiverse' proposed by Weinberg (1987) [¹²⁴] employs a varying 'cosmological constant' which our model also implies.

The underlying inconsistencies and discrepancies of the Planck anisotropies with the standard concordance model have been identified as potentially resolvable in Einstein-Cartan cosmology with clustered dark matter haloes and torsional OAM by Palle (2014) (¹²⁵) in general agreement to the basis of our discrete field dynamics. The case of 'apparent' FTL allowed by our model appears to offer resolution of the anomalous 'dynamic Casimir effect', the implications of which have also given rise to a speculative 'Toy Cosmology' at a Hubble scale (McCulloch 2014). [¹²⁶] Gamow was often attributed as promoting the Big Bang, but in fact was working on his 'big squeeze' model and reputedly rejected responsibility for turning Fred Hoyle's disparaging description 'Big Bang' into a paradigm. A typical early stage of the proposed cyclic galaxy dynamic does show similar peculiar helical, axial and wide angle dipole characteristics to those found in large scale CMBR anisotropies. The proposed cycle, if confirmed as consistent kinetically, may then prove to be a good enough fit to suggest a cosmic model worthy of further investigation.

9 Summary

We have outlined a proposal for a continuous evolutionary cycle of galaxy morphologies which includes a newly derived mechanism for the formation of bars. We describe the proposed cycle as a 'no feedback' mechanism, but may also be seen as a new $\sim < 100\%$ 'mass feedback' process. The role of toroidal AGN's is identified, as a nuclear tokamak counter-wound 'helicon' recycling mechanism, accreting, re-ionizing and ionizing new matter via quasar jet acceleration and ambient field interaction. In our hypothesis AGN's accrete and recycle the matter from whole discs, powered by orbital angular momentum and magnetic fields. Initial low speed mass outflow 'winds' form the expanding lobes of the bulge before jets break through at full power, precessing around the AGN axis and sending re-ionized matter and plasma through the old halo gases. The process 'evaporates' the AGN consistent with (Hawking, 2014) [¹²⁷] information preservation. The ionized jet arm matter is spread in a spiral column on an axis perpendicular to the old disc. The intrinsic rotation of matter

in space to a virial radius causes the central part of the column to rotate on the new primary axis. This new axis of rotation within the column virial radius forms the central bar. The outer ends of the column then trail due to the velocity gradient to form the spiral arms.

The rapid progress of the jet matter through the old halo promotes the Higgs process and additional matter at collimation shear surfaces. The peak star production at open spiral bar ends is due to the same pair production process. The ubiquitous but unexplained halo and satellite kinetic decoupling emerges naturally from our new models rotational axis change. The total mass and size of a galaxy will increase as a result of the ionization implicit in the high powered recycling process. The helicity of the columns will resolve to two arms from each bar end when rotating on the new axis. As rotation speed increases the spiral arms will tighten and blend into discs. Orbital angular momentum rebuilds and powers the new AGN ('SMBH') spin and *disc plane focused* accretion to start the new cycle.

We find that the two or possibly three peaks in quasar activity, since $z=11$, commonly denoted the 'Quasar Era's represent peaks of recycling activity, at least the last of which, at around $z\sim 1.7$ will have included the recycling of the Milky Way's disc matter. At $z=3$ our galaxy may then have been one of the old red disc galaxies with increasing lobe luminosity found in the significant but unexplained majority at that era. The proposed model outlined is also shown to suggest a new rationale and process for apparent superluminal jets found at $<46c$ which recovers the postulates of Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity by invoking collimation and two-fluid plasma dynamics and atomic scattering to local medium propagation speed c at all scales. The stochastic processes involved in the cycle guarantee quantitative uncertainty, but we identify relevant mathematical approximations. The iterative toy model and dynamic processes outlined herein would represent new physics, which will be falsifiable by kinematic observation and modelling including against data from the COS survey of feedback dynamics. We identify that evidence of significant feedback flow from jet to disc will falsify the cyclic model proposed, as might the confirmation of a genuine substantial merger population.

We have also described how a number of other galaxy characteristics and population distribution patterns not completely understood fit consistently within the proposed model. Possible additional insights are identified and we suggest other areas of useful detailed investigation and application. Some headings of subjects where our cyclic model suggests useful clarifications may emerge are as follows;

1. *Bars; Formation mechanisms and role in evolution.*
2. *Feedback; Reason for observed lack of feedback from jet outflows to disc.*
3. *The apparent quenching of star formation rates.*
4. *AGNs; The mechanism and key role of the active galactic nucleus (SMBH).*
5. *'Superluminal' Jets; Acceleration, role, structure and local frame limit c .*
6. *Conical outflows; cause of helicity and circular polarity.*
7. *Lobes; The formation of lobes and the peanut/boxy bulge morphology.*
8. *GRB's; Doppler mechanisms producing gamma ray bursts from quasars.*
9. *Shocks; Jet collimation, shear and electron shock 'heating'.*
10. *Kinematic decoupling; Halo & satellite galaxy orbital decoupling.*
11. *Dwarf spheroids; Formation and the core-cusp problem of satellites.*
12. *Morphology; Peculiar disc and satellite forms and age distributions.*
13. *Quasar era's; Importance of the peaks at $z \sim 10?$, $z \sim 6$, and $z \sim 1.7$.*
14. *Magellanic and similar 'matter streams'; Possible confirmation of cause.*
15. *Early-Late universe repetition of morphologies; Rationalisation.*
16. *Mass Growth; Cause of of galaxy mass and size growth $z=11 > z=1.5$.*
17. *Re-ionization; Methodology of hydrogen first, then later of helium.*
18. *Rings; The formation, dynamics and evolution of ring galaxies.*
19. *Stellar age and metallicity distributions; Reasons for peculiar pattern.*
20. *Modelling constraints; Causes of limits for semi-analytic n -body models.*

10 Acknowledgements.

We thank Legacy Archive for Microwave Background Data Analysis (LAMBDA), part of the High Energy Astrophysics Science Archive Center (HEASARC), part of the Astrophysics Science Division at the NASA Goddard Space Flight Centre.

- 1 Martini, P.; Weinberg, D.H. Quasar Clustering and the Lifetime of Quasars. *ApJ*, **2001**, 547 12
- 2 Micali, A.; Matteucci, F.; Romano, D. The chemical evolution of the Milky Way: the Three
3 Infall Model. *MNRAS*, **2013**, stt 1681.
- 4 Vogelsberger, M. et al. A model for cosmological simulations of galaxy formation physics.
5 *MNRAS*, **2013**, doi: stt1789.
- 6 Liu, G. et al. Observations of feedback from radio-quiet quasars – II. Kinematics of ionized
7 gas nebulae. *MNRAS*, **2013**, 10.1093/stt1755.
- 8 Lintott, C. et al. Galaxy Zoo 1: data release of morphological classifications for nearly 900
9 000 galaxies. *MNRAS*, **2010**, 410..166L.
- 10 Willett, K. et al. Galaxy Zoo 2: detailed morphological classifications for 304,122 galaxies
11 from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. *MNRAS*, **2013**, Vol. 435, Issue 4, p.2835-2860
- 12 Hoyle, B., et al. bar lengths in local disc galaxies. *MNRAS*, **2011**. 415 (4): 3627-3640.
- 13 Cabrera, J.I.; Coronado, Y.; Benitez, E.; Mendoza, S.; Hiriart, D.; Sorcia, M.; *MNRAS Lett.*
14 **2013**, 434: L6-L10.
- 15 Barro, G. et al, CANDELS: The progenitors of compact quiescent galaxies at $z \sim 2$. *ApJ*. 2012.
16 v765 104B.
- 17 Davis, R.L. et al. Galaxy Mapping with the SAURON Integral-Field Spectrograph: The Star
18 Formation History of NGC 4365. *ApJ*, **2001**, 584 L33D.
- 19 Barai, P.; Gopal-Krishna,; Osterman, M.A. Wiita, P.J. *Bulletin Asoc.I.* **2004**, v32 p.385-394.
- 20 Nesvadba, N.P.H. et al. The black holes of radio galaxies during the quasar Era Masses,
21 accretion rates, and evolutionary stage. *A & A*. **2010**, Acc. Nov. 14960.
- 22 Cimatti, A.; Nipoti C.; Cassata, P.; Fast evolving size of early-type galaxies at $z > 2$ and the
23 role of dissipationless (dry) merging. *MNRAS*, **2012**, 422 (1).
- 24 Dixon, K.L.; Furlanetto, S.R.; Mesinger, A. Semi-numeric simulations of helium reionization
25 and the fluctuating radiation background. *MNRAS*. Submitted June **2013**.
26 <http://arxiv.org/pdf/1306.1255.pdf>
- 27 Fontanot, F., Cristiani, S., Pfrommer, C., Cupani G., Vanzella, E., On the evolution of the
cosmic ionizing background. *MNRAS*. 2014, 10.1093/mnras/stt2332.
- 16 Sadowski, A.; Narayan, R.; Penna, R.; Zhu, Y. Energy, momentum and mass outflows and
feedback from thick accretion discs around rotating black holes. *MNRAS*, **2013**, 10.1093.1881
- 17 Arav, N.; Borguet, B.; Chamberlain, C.; Edmonds, D.; Danforth, C.; Quasar outflows and
AGN feedback in the extreme UV: *HST/COS* observations of HE 0238–1904 *MNRAS*, **2013**,
10.1093/mnras/stt1812.
- 18 Bolatto, A.D. et al. Suppression of star formation in the galaxy NGC 253 by a starburst-driven
molecular wind. *Nature*, **2013**, 499, 45053.
- 19 Werner, N. et al., A uniform metal distribution in the intergalactic medium of the Perseus
cluster of galaxies, *Nature* **2013**, 502, 656–658.
- 20 Parra, F.I.; Barnes, M.; Catto, P.J. Sources of intrinsic rotation in the low flow ordering.
Nuclear Fusion, **2011** 51 1133001. RPCtr. Th.Ph. Ox.
- 21 Parra, F.I.; Barnes, M.; Calvo, I.; Catto, P.J.; Intrinsic rotation with gyrokinetic models. *Phys.*
of Plasmas. **2012** 19, 056116.
- 22 Barnes, M. et al., Intrinsic rotation driven by non-Maxwellian equilibria in tokamak plasmas.
PRL **2013** v111. 5.
- 23 Romanelli, F.; Kamendje, R. Overview of JET results. *Nuclear Fusion* 49, **2009** 104006.
- 24 Wang, W.X.; Diamond, P.H.; Hahm, T.S.; Ethier, S.; Rewoldt, T.; Tang, W.M. Nonlinear flow
generation by electrostatic turbulence in tokamaks. *Physics of Plasmas* **2010** 17, 072511.
- 25 Kravtsov, A.V. The size-virial radius relation of galaxies. *ApJ*. **2013** 764 L31.
- 26 Buta, R.J.; Zhang, X. Pattern Corotation Radii from Potential-Density Phase-Shifts for 153
OSUBGS Sample Galaxies. *ApJ Supp.* **2010** 182, 559.
- 27 Ragone-Figueroa, C. et al. Brightest cluster galaxies in cosmological simulations:
achievements and limitations of active galactic nuclei feedback models. *MNRAS*, **2013**, 436.

- 28 Kaviraj, S.; Tan, K.-M.; Ellis, R. S.; Silk, J.; A coincidence of disturbed morphology and blue UV colour: minor-merger-driven star formation in early-type galaxies at $z \sim 0.6$ *MNRAS*, **2011**, 411 (4) 2148-2160.
- 29 Simmons, D.B. et al. Galaxy Zoo: bulgeless galaxies with growing black holes. *MNRAS* **2013** v429, p.2199-2211.
- 30 Debattista, V.P.; Kazantzidis, S.; van den Bosch, F.C. Disk Assembly and the M BH- σ_e Relation of Supermassive Black Holes. *ApJ* **2013** 765.1, 23.
- 31 Kavejari, S. et al, The insignificance of major mergers in driving star formation at $z \approx 2$. *MNRAS* **2013** 429.L40.
- 32 Jaeger, M. Thesis; Ruperto-Carola-University. May **2013**. http://www.mpia.de/imprs-hd/theses/thesis_jaeger.pdf (as at 27 Dec. 2013).
- 33 Brodwin, M. et al. "The Era of Star Formation in Galaxy Clusters. *ApJ*, **2013** 779, 138.
- 34 Urquhart, J.S. et al., The RMS survey: galactic distribution of massive star formation. *MNRAS* **2014**, (Jan.) 437 (2): p.1791-1807.
- 35 Keel, W.C. et al., The Galaxy Zoo survey for giant AGN-ionized clouds: past and present black hole accretion events. *MNRAS* **2012** 420.1 p.878-900.
- 36 Petty, S.M. et al. UV-bright nearby early type galaxies observed in the mid-infrared: evidence for a multi-stage formation history by way of WISE and GALEX imaging. *AJ* **2013**, v146.4. p.17-77.
- 37 Schnorr-Müller, A., Storchi-Bergmann, T., Nagar, N. M., Ferrari, F. Gas inflows towards the nucleus of the active galaxy NGC 7213 *MNRAS* 2014 438: 3322-3331
- 38 Aragon-Calvo, M. A., Yang, L. F. The hierarchical nature of the spin alignment of dark matter haloes in filaments *MNRASL*. **2014**, 10.1093/mnrasl/slu009
- 39 Li, Z.; Morris, M.R.; Baganoff, F.K. Evidence for A Parsec-scale Jet from The Galactic Center Black Hole: Interaction with Local Gas. *Astrophysical Journal*, **2013**, Accepted Nov.
- 40 Quillen, A. C. et al. A Vertical Resonance Heating Model for X- or Peanut-Shaped Galactic Bulges. *MNRAS*, **2013**, doi: 10.1093/mnras/stt1972.
- 41 Cortese, L. et al., "PACS photometry of the Herschel Reference Survey – far-infrared/ submillimeter colors as tracers of dust properties in nearby galaxies," *MNRAS*, online 17 March 2014. doi:10.1093/mnras/stu175
- 42 Durré, M and Jeremy Mould, J. "Young Star Clusters In The Circumnuclear Region Of NGC 2110," **2014**, *ApJ*, 784, 79. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1402.3339> (31.3.2014)
- 43 Kumar, R., Chattopadhyay, I., Mandal, S. Radiatively and thermally driven self-consistent bipolar outflows from accretion discs around compact objects. *MNRAS*. **2014**. 437(3)2 pp992-3003.
- 44 Wiebold, M. Low-Pressure Helicon-Plasma Discharge Initiation via Magnetic Field Ramping. *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*. **2009**, v.37, No. 11.
- 45 Suzuki-Vidal, F. et al. Observation of energetic protons trapped in laboratory magnetic-tower jets. *New J. Phys*, **2013**, 15 125008
- 46 Gabuzda, D.C.; Cantwell, T.M.; Cawthorne, T.V. Magnetic field structure of the extended 3C 380 jet., *MNRASL*, **2013**, 10.1093/mnras/slt129.
- 47 Bhat, P Eric G. Blackman, E. G., Subramanian, K. Resilience of helical fields to turbulent diffusion – II. Direct numerical simulations. *MNRAS* **2014** 438: 2954-2966.
- 48 Mendoza, S.; Hidalgo J.; Olvera D.; Cabrera J. Internal shocks in relativistic jets with time-dependent sources *MNRAS* **2009** 395. p.1403-1408.
- 49 Davies, P.C.W. Quantum vacuum friction. *J. Optics. B:* **2005** Quantum Semiclass. Opt.7 S40.
- 50 Porciani, C.; Magliocchetti, M.; Norberg, P. Cosmic evolution of quasar clustering: implications for the host haloes. *MNRAS* **2004** 355. 3. p1010-1030.
- 51 Kumar, R., Singh, C.B.; Chattopadhyay, I.; Chakrabarti, S.K. Effect of the flow composition on outflow rates from accretion discs around black holes., *MNRAS*, **2013** 436: p.2864-2873.
- 52 Prochaska, J. X., Piero Madau, P., O'Meara, J. M., Fumagalli, M. Towards a unified description of the intergalactic medium at redshift $z \approx 2.5$. *MNRAS* 2014 438: pp.476-486.

- 53 B. M. Walsh, et al., “Simultaneous Ground- and Space-Based Observations of the
Plasmaspheric Plume and Reconnection. *Science*. **2014**: Vol. 343 no. 6175. pp. 1122-1125;
- 54 Aberle C. Algorithm for Solving Colocated Electromagnetic Fields Including Sources.
University of Washington. Thesis. 2004. (link; 27 Dec. 2013).
- 55 Aberle C. Algorithm for Solving Colocated Electromagnetic Fields Including Sources.
University of Washington. Thesis. 2004. (link; 27 Dec. 2013).
https://www.aa.washington.edu/research/cpdlab/docs/MStthesis_aberle.pdf
- 56 Akhiezer, A.I.; Polovin, R.V. Theory of wave motion of an electron plasma. *Sov. Phys-JETP*,
1956; 3: p.696-705.
- 57 Salem, M., Bryan, G. L. Cosmic ray driven outflows in global galaxy disc models. *MNRAS*,
2014 437: pp.3312-3330.
- 58 Barkov, M., Komissarov, S.S., Korolev, V., Zankovich, A., A multidimensional numerical
scheme for **two-fluid** relativistic magnetohydrodynamics. *MNRAS* 2014 438: pp.704-716.
- 59 Er, X.; Mao, S. Effects of plasma on gravitational lensing., *MNRAS*, **2013**, 10.1093/stt2043.
- 60 Gao, S. Explaining Holographic Dark Energy. *Galaxies* **2013**, 1. p.180-191.
- 61 Sutter, P. M., Lavaux, G., Wandelt, B. D., Weinberg, D. H., Warren, M. S. The dark matter of
galaxy voids. *MNRAS* **2014** 438: 3177-3187
- 62 Jackson, P. A. Classical reproduction of quantum correlations. *Phys.Rev.X*. 2014, Submitted
23 March.
- 63 Jaroszynski, M., Kostrzewa-Rutkowska, Z. The influence of the matter along the line of sight
and in the lens environment on the strong gravitational lensing. 2014. *MNRAS*. pub. 5 Feb.
10.1093/mnras/stu096
- 64 Gardner, E.; Done, C. What powers the most relativistic jets? – I. BL Lacs. *MNRAS*, **2013**,
10.1093/mnras/stt2246.
- 65 Bogdan, A., et al. Exploring the unusually high black hole-to-bulge mass ratios in NGC 4342
and NGC4291: the asynchronous growth of bulges and black holes. Accepted *ApJ*. 2012.
- 66 Araudo, A.; Bosch-Ramon, V.; Gustavo E. Romero, G.E. Gamma-ray emission from massive
stars interacting with active galactic nuclei jets., *MNRAS*. **2013** Stt 1840.
- 67 Quenby, J.J.; Webber, W. R. The structure of the Heliopause. *MNRAS*, **2013**, stt1813.
- 68 Zdziarski, A. A.; Pjanka, P. Compton scattering of blackbody photons by relativistic electrons.
MNRAS, **2013**, stt1773.
- 69 Canate, P.; Perle, P.; Sudarski, D. Continuous spontaneous localization wave function collapse
model as a mechanism for the emergence of cosmological asymmetries in inflation. *Phys. Rev.*
D, **2013**, 87,104024.
- 70 Aksenov, A.G.; Ruffini, R.; Vereshchagin, G.V. Comptonization of photons near the
photosphere of relativistic outflows. *MNRASL*, **2013**, 436: L54-L58.
- 71 Shumlak, U.; Aberle C.; Hakim A.; Loverich J. Plasma Simulation Algorithm for the Two-
Fluid Plasma Model. EPS/APS Conference on Computational Physics. Div. of Computational
Physics. **2004**. https://www.aa.washington.edu/research/cpdlab/docs/shumlak_apscpp2004.pdf
(as at 27 Dec.2013).
- 72 Hirota, M., Morrison, P. J., Hattori, Y., Variational Necessary and Sufficient Stability
Conditions for Inviscid Shear Flow. 2014. sub. Proc. R.Soc. Lond. A .
<http://arxiv.org/pdf/1402.0719v1.pdf>
- 73 Bégué, D., Vereshchagin, G.V., Transparency of an instantaneously created electron–positron–
photon plasma. 2014, *MNRAS* pub. 31 Jan., 10.1093/mnras/stu011.
<http://arxiv.org/abs/1401.1413>
- 74 Powers, N.D. Et al. Quasi-monoenergetic and tunable X-rays from a laser-driven Compton
light source. *Nature Photonics*, **2013**, Online 24th Nov.
- 75 Ehrenstein, D. Conjuring Matter From Light. *Science*, **1997**, Vol 277, No 5330 AAAS. p 1202.
- 76 Higuchi, T., Tamara, H., Kuwata-Gonomaki, M. Selection rules for angular momentum transfer
via impulsive stimulated Raman scattering. *PRA* **2013** 87, 013808.

- 77 Melvin T. et al., Galaxy Zoo: an independent look at the evolution of the bar fraction over the last eight billion years from *HST-COSMOS*. **2014**, MNRAS, 16 Jan. 10.1093/mnras/stt2397
- 78 Cordes, J.M.; Pidwerbetsky A.; Lovelace, R.V.E., Refractive and diffractive scattering in the interstellar medium *ApJ*, **1986** 310, 737.
- 79 Rickett, B.J.; Coles, W.A.; The Impact of VLBI on Astrophysics and Geophysics, ed. M. J. Reid & J. M. Moran. 28794. *IAU Symp.* **1988**, Vol. 129.
- 80 Pushkarev, A.B. et al. VLBA observations of a rare multiple quasar imaging event caused by refraction in the interstellar medium. *A & A*. **2013** 555. A80.
- 81 Liberati, S.; Tests of Lorentz invariance: a 2013 update. *Classical and Quantum Gravity*. **2013**. 30, 133001.
- 82 Jackson, P. A.; Minkowski, J. S.; Resolution of Kantor and Babcock-Bergman Emission Theory Anomalies. *Hadronic Jnl*. **2012** 5, vol 35. p.527-556.
- 83 Cohen, J.G.; Kirby, E.N. The bizarre chemical inventory of NGC 2419, an extreme outer halo globular cluster. *ApJ*, **2012**, 760:86.
- 84 Rothenstein, B. Galilean relativity, special relativity and the work-kinetic energy theorem revisited. **2007**. <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2007physics...3280R> (as at 27 Dec. 2013).
- 85 Feigenbaum, M.J.; The Theory of Relativity Galileo's Child. **2008**. <http://arxiv.org/pdf/0806.1234v1.pdf> (as at 27 Dec. 2013).
- 86 Kaplan, G. The IAU Resolutions on Astronomical Reference Systems, Time Scales, and Earth Rotation Models. USNO Circ. No.179. **2005**
- 87 Meyer, E.T. et al. Optical Proper Motion Measurements of the M87 Jet: New Results from the Hubble Space Telescope. *ApJ*, **2013** 774, L21.
- 88 Junor, W.; Biretta, J. A.; Livio, M. Formation of the radio jet in M87 at 100 Schwarzschild radii from the central black hole. *Nature* **1999** 401: p.891-892.
- 89 Paczynski, B. Gamma-ray bursters at cosmological distances, *ApJ*, **1986**, v308, L43-46.
- 90 Goodman, J. Are gamma-ray bursts optically thick? *ApJ*, **1986**, 308, L47-50.
- 91 Rees, M.; *Cosmic Jets*. 1985. NASA. Goddard Space Flight Center Nineteenth International Cosmic Ray Conference. Vol. 9 17 p (SEE N86-31483 22-93)
- 92 Rees, M.J.; Meszaros, P. Unsteady outflow models for cosmological gamma-ray bursts. *ApJ*, **1994** 430.2 pt.2. L93-96.
- 93 Duffell, P.C.; MacFadyen, A.I. A "Boosted Fireball" Model for Structured Relativistic Jets. *ApJ*, **2013**, **776** L9.
- 94 Sumner, W.Q.; On the variation of vacuum permittivity in Friedmann Universes. *ApJ*, **1994**. 429; p.491-498,.
- 95 Mundell, C.G. et al., Highly polarized light from stable ordered magnetic fields in GRB 120308A. **2013**. *Nature* 504, pp.119–121.
- 96 Ciolfi, R.; Rezzolla, L. Twisted-torus configurations with large toroidal magnetic fields in relativistic stars. *MNRAS*, **2013**. 435 L43-L47.
- 97 O'Sullivan, S.P.; McClure-Griffiths, N.M., Feain, I.J., Gaensler, B.M., Sault, R.J. Broadband radio circular polarization spectrum of the relativistic jet in PKS B2126? **2013**, 158 *MNRAS*
- 98 Chin, S.L. *Femtosecond Laser Filamentation*. Atomic Optical and Plasma Physics. Vol. 55. (Springer, Berlin, 2010).
- 99 Polynkin, P. et al. Seeded optically driven avalanche ionization in molecular and noble gases. *PRA* **2012** 86, 043410.
- 100 Laing, R.A. Bridle, A. H. Systematic properties of decelerating relativistic jets in low-luminosity radio galaxies. *MNRAS*, 2013 437: 3405-3441.
- 101 Reodiger, E et al.; Viscous Kelvin–Helmholtz instabilities in highly ionized plasmas. *MNRAS*, **2013**. 436(2).1721.
- 102 Blandford, R. D.; Znajek R.L. Electromagnetic extraction of energy from Kerr black holes *MNRAS*, **1977**, 179: p.433-456.
- 103 Cappellari M., et al. The SAURON project – X. The orbital anisotropy of elliptical and lenticular galaxies: revisiting the $(V/\sigma, \epsilon)$ diagram with integral-field stellar kinematics.

- MNRAS* **2007** 379.2. p.418-444.
- 104 Hernández-Monteagudo C.; Ho S. On the peculiar momentum of baryons after re-ionization. *MNRAS*, **2009**, v398 2. p.790-806.
- 105 Biffi, V.; Maio, U. Statistical properties of mass, star formation, chemical content and rotational patterns in early $z > 9$ structures. *MNRAS*, **2013**. 10.1093/mnras/stt1678. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1309.2283>
- 106 Katkov, I. Y., Sil'chenko, O.K., Afanasiev, V. L. Decoupled gas kinematics in isolated S0 galaxies. *MNRAS* **2014** 438: 2798-2803
- 107 Peebles, P. J. E.; Phelps, S.D.; Shaya E.J.; Tully, R.B. Radial and Transverse Velocities of Nearby Galaxies. *AJ*. **2001** 554. pp.104-113.
- 108 McDermid, R.M.; Peltier, R.F. On the origin and fate of ionised-gas in early-type galaxies: The SAURON perspective. *New Astronomical Reviews* **2007** 51. 1-2, 18-23. 184.
- 109 Rees, B.; Zijlstra, A.A. Alignment of the angular momentum vectors of planetary nebulae in the Galactic Bulge. *MNRAS* **2013** Vol. 435 p.975-991
- 110 Nodland, B., Ralston, J.P., Indication of Anisotropy in Electromagnetic Propagation over Cosmological Distances. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1997**. 78, pp3043–3046
- 111 Emsellem, E., et al. The SAURON project - IX. A kinematic classification for early-type galaxies. *MNRAS*, **2007**, 379 p401-417.
- 112 Emsellem, E. et al. The ATLAS3D project - III. A census of the stellar angular momentum within the effective radius of early-type galaxies: unveiling the distribution of fast and slow rotators. *MNRAS*, **2011**, 414 2. p.888-912.
- 113 Amelino-Camelia, G.; Fiore, F.; Guetta, D.; Puccetti, S.; Quantum-spacetime scenarios and soft spectral lags of the remarkable GRB130427A. *Advances in High Energy Physics*. **2014**. 597384, Vol.2014. (pp16). <http://arxiv.org/pdf/1305.2626.pdf>
- 114 Williams, M.E.K. et al. The wobbly Galaxy: kinematics north and south with RAVE red-clump giants. *MNRAS*, **2013**, 10.1093/mnras/stt1522.
- 115 Shaya, E.J.; Brent Tully, R. The formation of Local Group planes of galaxies. *MNRAS*, **2013**. 10.1093/mnras/stt1714.
- 116 Knebe, A.; Gill, S.P.D.; Gibson, B.K.; Lewis, G.F.; Ibata, R.A.; Dopita, M.A. Anisotropy in the Distribution of Satellite Galaxy Orbits. *ApJ* **2004** v603 p.7-11.
- 117 Ogiya, G.; Mori, M.; The core-cusp problem in cold dark matter halos and supernova feedback: Effects of Mass Loss. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* **2011**, 736 L2.
- 118 Cignoni, et al. Mean age gradient and asymmetry in the star formation history of the Small Magellanic Cloud. accepted for publication in *ApJ* **2013**. 775. 83.
- 119 Belokurov, V.; et al. Precession of the Sagittarius stream. *MNRAS* **2013**, 437: p.116-131.
- 120 awlowski, M. S.; Kroupa, P. The rotationally stabilized VPOS and predicted proper motions of the Milky Way satellite galaxies. *MNRAS*, **2013**. Vol.435 p.2116-2131.
- 121 Bland-Hawthorn, J.; Maloney, P.R.; Sutherland, R.S.; Madsen, G.J.. Fossil Imprint of a Powerful Flare at the Galactic Center Along the Magellanic Stream. *AJ*. **2013**. Sept. Acc.
- 122 Markoff, S.; et al. Results from an Extensive Simultaneous Broadband Campaign on the Underluminous Active Nucleus M81*: Further Evidence for Mass-scaling Accretion in Black Holes. *The Astrophysical Journal*, **2008**, 681 905.
- 123 Kunz et al 2009. *Phys Rev.D* **80** 083533
- 124 Weinberg, S. 1987 *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **59** 2607
- 125 Palle, D., On The Einstein-Cartan Cosmology. *Planck Data*. 2014. *JETP*, Vol. 118, No. 4.
- 126 McCulloch, M.E. A Toy Cosmology Using a Hubble-Scale Casimir Effect. *Galaxies* **2014**, 2, 81-88. <http://www.mdpi.com/2075-4434/2/1/81>
- 127 Hawking, S. R. Information Preservation and Weather Forecasting for Black Holes. Jan **2014**. DAMTP. Camb. <http://arxiv.org/pdf/1401.5761v1.pdf>